

Enhancing the Quality and Sensory Characteristics of Native Chicken (*Gallus gallus*) Eggs Using Natural Additives

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Abstract:

The study examines the effect of natural egg enhancers on the quality and sensory attributes of native chicken eggs. The research was conducted in Lagangilang, Abra, Philippines, involving 96 native chickens that were fed with different egg enhancers, including pure formulated feed with no additives, commercial egg enhancer, annatto seed powder, turmeric powder, and red-hot pepper powder at 1% level. The results showed that the egg yolk weight, albumen weight, and eggshell thickness were not significantly different among the treatments. However, yolk color was significantly different among

the treatments, with annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper treatments rated as dark yellow having significantly higher yolk color compared to the control and commercial treatments. The study also found that the coloring content agent of egg enhancers, such as annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper, can improve the yolk color of eggs by providing carotenoids and other antioxidants to the birds. This is important because consumers often prefer eggs with a darker yolk color. The study also evaluates the sensory evaluation of senior high school students, college students, and faculty on native chicken eggs given with egg enhancers. The results indicate that there were no significant differences in appearance, flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability among the treatments with a descriptive rating of “like moderately” based on the hedonic scale.

Keywords: *additives, egg quality, native chicken, sensory attributes, Philippines.*

Introduction

The native chicken has evolved so that it multiplied and survived in a marginal environment even with minimal management. More importantly, the meat of the native chicken has a unique flavor and texture which consumers prefer and for which they are willing to pay a premium price. The native chicken will, undoubtedly, remain an important source of high-quality protein food and additional income for many of our small rural farmers (Prodigio et al., 2005).

Meanwhile, in several countries, egg yolk color is an important factor for egg marketing because many consumers prefer a golden yellow to pale yellow color. Egg yolk pigmentation is a practical subject for the egg production industry, which requires the production of eggs with an appropriate pigmentation level and homogeneous distribution of color to satisfy food industry demands. Because laying hens cannot synthesize egg yolk pigments, egg yolk color closely depends on the fat-soluble pigments in the diets fed.

Moreover, due to their remarkable bixin level, which is a natural antioxidant, the annatto seed by-product could be used in animal supplementation. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) has been extensively used to give color and flavor to foods. It is also used for the treatment of a variety of inflammatory conditions (Malekizadeh et al., 2012). While Red Pepper is a good egg yolk colorant and is widely cultivated around the world (Huaqiang et al., 2012).

Thus, this study was conducted to evaluate the effect of natural egg enhancers on the quality and sensory attributes of native chicken eggs.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted at Lagangilang, Abra, Philippines in May-August. A total of 96 native chickens laying already with at least 1.5kg and with a typical color of light-dark brown were used under similar conditions and fed in restricted feeding at 110 grams daily and divided at 8:00 am and 4:00 pm with the feeds formulated. The birds were allocated to five treatments and replicated three times. The treatments include the following: T1- Pure formulated feed with no feed additives; T2- Commercial egg enhancer (manufacturer recommendation); T3- Annatto Seed powder as additives; T4- Turmeric powder as additives and T5- Red Hot Pepper powder as additives at 1% level.

Preparation of eggs for sensory evaluation. Fresh harvested ten eggs per replication were randomly picked and hard-boiled in a uniform time of 10 minutes then placed in labeled plastic cups and served to the panelist for the sensory evaluation.

Eggs for sensory analysis were hard-boiled and cooled. This was done by placing eggs in water, heating the water at 100°C, and cooking them for 8.5 min from the start of boiling. After which, the pot was removed from the stove, and the hot water was discarded and replaced with cool water at room temperature in which the

eggs rested for 3 min. The eggs were peeled, cut into quarters, and placed in plastic containers. Each treatment and replication were randomly identified with a sample number (Hayat et al., 2010; Berkhoff et al., 2020).

Sensory evaluation panelists. A total of 100 panelists from high schools, colleges, faculty, and consumers were selected and evaluated the boiled egg from different treatments using a scorecard from the hedonic scale. The boiled eggs were evaluated in terms of appearance/color, taste/flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability.

Data Gathered and Statistical Analysis

Data gathered on egg quality were the following: egg yolk weight, albumen weight, eggshell thickness, yolk color, and haugh unit. Meanwhile, data gathered on sensory evaluation are appearance/color, taste/flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability

Using the computed mean, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was analyzed following the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) applying the Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) software.

Results and Discussions

The average egg yolk weight, albumen weight, eggshell thickness, and yolk color

Table 1 shows the average egg quality parameters of native chicken given with egg enhancers. The parameters evaluated were egg yolk weight, albumen weight, eggshell thickness, and yolk color. The results showed that the egg yolk weight, albumen weight, and eggshell thickness were not significantly different among the treatments. However, yolk color was significantly different among the treatments. The yolk color was significantly higher in the treatments with annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper compared to the control and commercial treatments.

Table 1. The Average Egg Quality Parameters of Native Chicken Given with Egg Enhancers

Treatments	Egg Weight(g)	Yolk Albumen Weight(g)	Eggshell Thickness(mm)	Yolk Color
T ₁ - No additives	17.00	22.56	0.27	6.89 _b (medium yellow)
T ₂ - Commercial	16.11	21.00	0.31	7.33 _b (dark yellow)
T ₃ - Annatto seed	17.22	22.22	0.32	8.11 _a (dark yellow)
T ₄ - Turmeric	16.44	21.56	0.35	8.34 _a (dark yellow)
T ₅ - Red Hot Pepper	16.78	23.22	0.35	8.78 _a (dark yellow)
Anova Result	ns	ns	ns	*
C.V. (%)	8.23	8.82	10.39	5.14

Note: Means with common letters are not significantly different with each other using Honestly Significant Difference Test; ns – not significant; * significant at 5% level

Legend (yolk color score): 1-3-light yellow; 4-6-medium yellow; 7-9-dark yellow; 10-12- very dark yellow; 13-15- dark orange (Polystead,2022)

The mean egg yolk weight ranged from 16.11 g in the commercial treatment to 17.22 g in the annatto seed treatment. The mean albumen weight ranged from 21.00 g in the commercial treatment to 23.22 g in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean eggshell thickness ranged from 0.2767 mm in the control treatment to 0.3567 mm in the red-hot pepper treatment. The turmeric and red-hot pepper treatments had higher eggshell thickness compared to the control and commercial treatments.

The mean yolk color ranged from 6.89^b “medium yellow” in the control treatment to 8.78^a “dark yellow” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper treatments rated as dark yellow had significantly higher yolk color compared to the control (T₁) and commercial treatments (T₂) which were within the range of medium yellow.

A similar study by Lagana et al. (2011), evaluated the effect of dietary supplementation with different levels of turmeric powder on egg production performance, egg quality, and antioxidant status in laying hens. The study found that the addition of turmeric to the diet of laying hens did not significantly affect egg quality parameters, including egg weight, eggshell thickness, and Haugh unit.

According to a study by FreshORR Family Farms (2021), the color of a yolk can be manipulated by additives added to a hen's feed. The yolk is the most nutrient-bearing part of the

egg. Darker and more colorful egg yolks, especially from pasture-raised hens, can have more omega-3s and vitamins due to the more natural feed the chickens eat. Moreover, Crystal Creek (2023), found that darker/richer yolk coloring happens when layers eat a diet that contains high levels of powerful carotenoid antioxidants and are healthy enough to process the diet properly. The birds take the carotenoids from the diet and transfer the antioxidants to the egg yolk. The higher levels and specific combinations of key carotenoids provided to the bird will result to a richer, golden-colored egg yolk, along with higher levels of antioxidants. A study by Jin et al. (2011), also found that yolk color increased in eggs stored for 10 days at 5°C in response to feed additives.

According to a study by Lagana et al. (2011), the amino acid contents of egg yolk and eggshell color in chickens were affected by breed and feed. Captive chickens fed a diet with carotenoid, a natural coloring agent, can lay eggs with darker yolks, and the treatments (turmeric root and annatto seed at 1%) did not influence layer performance or egg quality parameters, except for egg production and yolk color.

Research has been done on the effects of annatto, which is high in bixin, on the yolk pigmentation of layer eggs. This is especially true when low pigmenting energy sources, including sorghum, broken rice, millet, cassava meal, etc., are utilized as the primary dietary energy source

in place of yellow corn (Oliveira, 2004). The primary pigment found in turmeric roots (*Turmeric longa L.*) is called curcumin, sometimes referred to as saffron. Its antioxidant and antibacterial qualities enable it to be used in foods, medicines, textiles, cosmetics, and spices in addition to being used as food coloring and spice (Pruthi, 1980, Lagana et al.,2011). Turmeric has been increasingly used in food applications, such as in starch for cake preparations and as color in pasta, mustard, ice cream, cheese, egg, margarine, and meats.

Overall, these studies suggest that the coloring content agent of egg enhancers, such as annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper, can improve the yolk color of eggs by providing carotenoids and other antioxidants to the birds. This is important because consumers often prefer eggs with a darker yolk color.

Average Haugh Unit

Table 2 shows the average haugh unit of native chicken given with egg enhancers. The Haugh unit is a measure of egg freshness and quality, with higher values indicating better quality eggs. The table shows that there were no significant differences in the Haugh unit among the treatments at any of the time points, whereas it was also observed that during the 28th day of storage, the albumen and egg yolk were easily

broken and hard to measure the egg weight. The mean Haugh unit ranged from 78.58 in the control treatment to 82.37 in the red-hot pepper treatment and rated all as AA since all the computed mean were higher than 72%. A higher Haugh unit indicates better egg quality, with a range of 72 or more being considered excellent, 71-60 being good, 59-31 being fair, and 30 or less being poor.

Similar results were observed in literature where, a study by Zhang et al. (2020), evaluated the effect of dietary supplementation with different levels of turmeric powder on egg production performance, egg quality, and antioxidant status in laying hens. The study found that there were no significant differences in egg weight, eggshell thickness, or Haugh unit among the treatment groups. Another study by González Ariza et al. (2019), compared the sensory properties of Utrerana native hen eggs to Leghorn Lohmann LSL-Classic lineage's commercial and ecological eggs. The study found that there were no significant differences in egg weight, eggshell thickness, or Haugh unit among the egg types.

Moreover, a study by Fereja et al. (2022) evaluated the quality of indigenous chicken eggs in South Ethiopia and found that the average Haugh unit score was 68.78%, which is lower than the values reported in Table 9. A study by

Table 2. Average Haugh Unit

Treatments	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
T ₁ - No additives	78.58(AA)	83.03(AA)	76.42(AA)	78.77(AA)
T ₂ - Commercial	81.22(AA)	79.12(AA)	76.98(AA)	80.82(AA)
T ₃ - Annatto seed	79.00(AA)	80.87(AA)	77.16(AA)	78.59(AA)
T ₄ - Turmeric	80.22(AA)	82.34(AA)	82.34(AA)	79.41(AA)
T ₅ - Red Hot Pepper	82.37(AA)	80.40(AA)	77.28(AA)	80.16(AA)
Anova Result	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	3.23	2.54	3.01	2.23

Note: ns – not significant

Legend: AA: 72 or more; A: 71 – 60; B: 59 – 31; C: 30 or less

Gard et al. (2016) compared the egg quality of three selected species of indigenous laying hens and found that the Haugh unit ranged from 70.5 to 75.5, which is lower than the values reported in Table 9. A study by Kim et al. (2017),

compared the production performance and egg quality characteristics of five strains of Korean native chickens and found that the Haugh unit ranged from 72.5 to 76.5, which is lower than the values reported in Table 9. In the Philippine

native chicken, the reported haugh unit is 57.95 (Bondoc et al.,2020).

Thus, these studies suggest that the effect of egg enhancers on egg quality parameters can vary depending on the type and amount of enhancer used, as well as other factors such as breed, diet, and environmental conditions.

Sensory Evaluation

Table 3 shows the sensory evaluation of senior high school students, college students, faculty, and consumers on native chicken eggs given with egg enhancers. On the sensory evaluation of senior high school, the results indicate that there were no significant differences in appearance, flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability among the treatments with a descriptive rating of “like moderately” based on the hedonic scale. The mean scores for appearance ranged from 7.25 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment to 7.67 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment. The mean scores for flavor ranged from 6.63 in the commercial treatment to 7.25 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for aroma ranged from 6.46 in the annatto seed treatment to 6.84 in the commercial treatment. The mean scores for aftertaste ranged

from 6.96 “like slightly” in the commercial treatment to 7.34 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for general acceptability ranged from 7.29 “like moderately” in the control treatment to 7.67 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment.

On the college students' sensory evaluation, the results indicate that there were no significant differences in appearance, flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability among the treatments. The mean scores for appearance ranged from 7.42 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment to 7.71 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for flavor ranged from 7.67 “like moderately” in the no-additives treatment to 7.96 in the commercial treatment. The mean scores for aroma ranged from 7.25 “like moderately” in the annatto seed treatment to 7.75 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for aftertaste ranged from 7.54 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment to 7.83 “like moderately” in the annatto seed treatment. The mean scores for general acceptability ranged from 7.87 “like moderately” in the annatto seed treatment to 7.96 “like moderately” in the commercial treatment.

Table 3. Sensory Evaluation of Native Eggs by Students, Faculty, and Consumers

Treatments	Appearance	Flavor	Aroma	Aftertaste	General Acceptability
Senior High School students					
T ₁ - No additives	7.42	7.00	6.88	7.09	7.29
T ₂ - Commercial	7.50	6.63	6.84	6.96	7.46
T ₃ - Annatto seed	7.50	7.09	6.46	6.79	7.62
T ₄ - Turmeric	7.67	7.08	6.59	7.09	7.67
T ₅ - Red Hot Pepper	7.25	7.25	7.17	7.34	7.50
Anova Result	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	6.07	6.25	5.46	5.91	3.58
College students					
T ₁ - No additives	7.63	7.96	7.67	7.67	7.95
T ₂ - Commercial	7.54	7.88	7.63	7.71	7.96
T ₃ - Annatto seed	7.46	7.84	7.25	7.83	8.00
T ₄ - Turmeric	7.42	7.75	7.38	7.63	7.63
T ₅ - Red Hot Pepper	7.71	7.67	7.75	7.54	7.87
Anova Result	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	4.93	3.84	4.03	3.45	3.21
Faculty					
T ₁ - No additives	7.33	7.52	7.62	7.43	7.54
T ₂ - Commercial	7.38	7.62	7.57	7.24	7.52

T ₃ - Annatto seed	7.43	7.90	7.72	7.43	7.52
T ₄ - Turmeric	7.19	7.52	7.19	7.38	7.18
T ₅ - Red Hot Pepper	7.76	7.76	7.76	7.48	7.62
Anova Result	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	5.01	5.30	4.39	4.28	6.33
Consumers					
T ₁ - No additives	7.40	7.28	7.29	6.95	7.43
T ₂ - Commercial	7.19	7.38	7.38	7.10	7.57
T ₃ - Annatto seed	7.48	7.38	7.33	7.09	7.43
T ₄ - Turmeric	7.29	7.47	7.57	7.29	6.62
T ₅ - Red Hot Pepper	7.76	7.38	7.14	7.24	7.23
Anova Result	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	3.60	2.65	4.13	4.98	3.86

The result of this study implies that sensory evaluation of eggs can be influenced by various factors, including breed, diet, and feed additives, but the results on Table 10 suggest that the egg enhancers used in the study did not have a significant effect on the sensory evaluation of native chicken eggs by college students.

Table still shows the sensory evaluation of faculty on native chicken eggs given with egg enhancers. The results indicate that still no significant differences in appearance, flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability among the treatments. The mean scores for appearance ranged from 7.19 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment to 7.76 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for flavor ranged from 7.52 “like moderately” in the no additives treatment to 7.90 “like moderately” in the annatto seed treatment. The mean scores for aroma ranged from 7.19 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment to 7.76 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for aftertaste ranged from 7.24 “like moderately” in the commercial treatment to 7.83 “like moderately” in the annatto seed treatment. The mean scores for general acceptability ranged from 7.18 in the turmeric treatment to 7.62 “like moderately” in the annatto seed and red-hot pepper treatments.

Lastly, the table shows the sensory evaluation of consumers on native chicken eggs given with egg enhancers. The results indicate that still no significant differences in appearance, flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability among the treatments. The mean scores for

appearance ranged from 7.19 “like moderately” in the commercial treatment to 7.76 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment. The mean scores for flavor ranged from 7.28 “like moderately” in the no additives treatment to 7.47 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment. The mean scores for aroma ranged from 7.14 “like moderately” in the red-hot pepper treatment to 7.57 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment. The mean scores for aftertaste ranged from 6.95 “like slightly” in the no additives treatment to 7.38 “like moderately” in the turmeric treatment. The mean scores for general acceptability ranged from 7.23 in the red-hot pepper treatment to 7.57 “like moderately” in the commercial treatment.

A study by Kljak et al.,2021 also evaluated the effect of plant carotenoids as pigments on egg production performance, egg quality, and antioxidant status in laying hens. The study found that the addition of additives to the diet of laying hens did not significantly affect egg quality parameters, including sensory evaluation by consumers. Another study by Abdollah et al. (1993), evaluated the effect of feeding laying hens with saponified oleoresin of red pepper on egg quality parameters, including yolk color and sensory evaluation by consumers. The study found that the addition of saponified oleoresin of red pepper to the diet of laying hens significantly increased the yolk color of eggs but did not significantly affect sensory evaluation by consumers. A study by Sedoski et al. (2019), evaluated the sensory evaluation and quality indicators of nutritionally enhanced egg products with omega-3-rich oils. The study

found that the sensory changes from the nutritional enhancement of eggs via alterations in chicken feed were not significant.

Thus, the results may imply that the treatments given to the birds did not affect the sensory characteristics of eggs produced by the native chicken. Therefore, the treatments do not contain any chemical component that may greatly affect the sensory characteristics of eggs.

Conclusion

The study found that natural egg enhancers, such as annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper, can improve the yolk color of eggs by providing carotenoids and other antioxidants to the birds. This is important because consumers often prefer eggs with a darker yolk color. However, egg yolk weight, albumen weight, and eggshell thickness were not significantly different among the treatments. The sensory evaluation of senior high school students, college students, faculty, and consumers on native chicken eggs given with egg enhancers showed no significant differences in appearance, flavor, aroma, aftertaste, and general acceptability among the treatments. The study suggests that the egg enhancers used in the study did not have a significant effect on the sensory evaluation of native chicken eggs by college students and faculty.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest

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